

The role played by non-stoichiometric phases on the expansion of alumina-based refractories during the *in-situ* formation of ZnAl_2O_4 and MgAl_2O_4

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ABSTRACT

Refractories containing *in-situ* formed spinel-like phases gained popularity in the 1990s due to their suitable properties and low environmental impact. Whereas magnesium aluminate is the most widely used compound, recent research highlights the benefits of alternative spinels, such as zinc aluminate. However, the *in-situ* generation of these phases implies challenges due to their high expansion, which exceeds the predicted values. Such deviations have been attributed to Kirkendall-induced pores, which sparks controversy. Fortunately, the evolving understanding of non-stoichiometric phases and computational techniques capable of predicting their properties allow the assessment of the formation of non-stoichiometric spinel-like phases that could account for such behavior, offering an integrative theory to elucidate the experimental results. In this study, thermodynamic calculations and data obtained through DFT were employed to predict the theoretical dimensional variation of non-stoichiometric gahnite and spinel formation. The obtained data were compared with measurements from dilatometry and sequential firings. Finally, X-ray diffraction and SEM/EDS analyses were used to track down the reaction pathway aiming at developing a unified theory capable of explaining and predicting the volumetric changes observed during the *in-situ* formation of both phases.

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